

Online Shopping during COVID-19: A study about the Perception of Foreign Students in China

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

The e-commerce industry in China is emerging day by day. The online shopping is increasing among Chinese consumers as well as foreigners in China. During the COVID-19 China used their e-commerce technology to reach every corner of the country providing the facility to purchase daily essentials. This research investigated the perception of foreign students about online shopping during the COVID-19 period in China. The study indicated the factors influenced to do the online shopping and the challenges faced by the foreign students of using online shopping apps during the epidemic period in China. This study uses a mix methodological and the data collection used quantitative and qualitative methods. The quantitative data was collected with the help of survey questionnaires while the qualitative data was collected with semi-structured questions. The descriptive analysis and the regression analysis were conducted to analyze the raw data.

The study tested six hypotheses of which the result showed that five hypotheses were in favor while one was against the assumption. The results indicated that there is a positive perception of foreign students towards using the online shopping apps during the COVID-19 period. It also indicated that foreign students are satisfied with online shopping during the COVID-19 period. The trustworthiness, efficiency and user friendliness became the positive factors of online shopping during the epidemic period and cost effectiveness indicated the negative impact on using online shopping apps. The study indicated the language as one of the main challenges of online shopping in China. The author suggested to have multiple language option in the apps as it will be more effective for all types of users.

Keywords: ONLINE SHOPPING, TRUSTWORTHINESS, EFFICIENCY, USERFRIENDLINESS, COSTEFFECTIVENESS, PERCEPTION

Introduction

Internet changed the regular life style of the people around the world. The swift growth of online shopping has international marketers scrambling to learn how to connect with this already large and still rapidly

growing Chinese consumer market. Worldwide, the Internet is the fastest growing retail channel. In 2005, a survey conducted by Chinese Academy of Social Sciences showed that although China is the second largest Internet market with more than 100 million Internet users, still the online shopping behavior is slowly growing. In 2012, as a result of an increasing Chinese consumer acceptance of e-commerce, China's 193 million online shoppers outnumbered the 170 million US online shoppers (Zheng, 2012). Chinese e-commerce has attracted the attention of many analysts. According to a Boston Consulting Group's (BCG) report, in 2015 China's online retail sales are expected to reach \$360 billion that year (Zheng, 2012). According to China's Ministry of Commerce October 2013 report, online shopping was the fastest growing retail channel of distribution with an annual growth of 26.5%, compared to supermarkets' growth of 9% and exclusive stores' growth of 8.4%. China started to develop the e-commerce and it became the future of China. Online shopping is becoming increasingly popular for variety of reasons. Factors such as increasing gas prices, difficulty in getting to traditional stores and hassles often associated with shopping malls and other traditional stores to contribute to the increased interest in online shopping.

As China is the most populated country in the world, online shopping quickly became popular among the consumers. People started to purchase most of the needy items from online and it developed day by day with good technology and accessibility. Recently, as the Corona virus outbreak started in late 2019, many people were forced to stay indoors. The educational institutes, shopping malls and offices closed. Most schools from basic to universities have shut down their doors and students have returned home to their parents and together self-quarantined (UNESCO, 2020). The global academic calendar has been thrown into a state of disarray by the Coronavirus outbreak. Never before have we witnessed educational disruption on such a large scale'' said UNESCO Director General Audrey Azoulay (2020).

China became the home of the Corona virus after it started to spread rapidly from the second week of January. As many cities were on lockdown, and the government of China instructed people to stay home unless it is necessary, many people including the foreign students became the victim of this. Though many countries send their special flights to evacuate their own students, millions of foreign students still had to stay in China during this period. It became very unusual time for foreign students as they had no option than buying necessary things online. Foreign students had to buy all the essential items such as rice, vegetables, meat, fruits etc. through online shopping apps which was normally not the case. The main objectives of this research are to identify the perception of foreigners regarding online shopping apps, satisfactory level of using the apps, the factors and reasons for using the online shopping apps and the challenges of using the apps during the COVID-19 period in China.

Hence, this study has tried to find the answers of following questions:

- Q1: What is the perception of foreign students about the online shopping apps during COVID-19?
- Q2: How much satisfied are the students with online shopping apps during the COVID-19?
- Q3: What are the factors for using the online shopping apps during the COVID-19?
- Q4: What are the challenges faced with online shopping during the COVID-19?
- Q5: What are the commonly used online shopping apps during the COVID-19?

This is a mix methodology research and the data were collected through interviews and questionnaires. Therefore, it is very interesting to find out the perception of foreign student's use of the online shopping apps during the pandemic in China

Literature Review

Since the turn of the 21st century, with the rapid development of Internet technology and cross-border e-commerce around the world, international trade players and trade patterns have been undergoing major changes. These changes have promoted the inclusive development of the world economy and international trade, and provided historic opportunities for the development of small and medium-sized enterprises (Lal, 2014)

China's e-commerce market is a very busy place, with the average online shopper purchasing ten items per quarter. It set to get even busier, with three in four claiming to have recently increased their rate of online shopping. China's e-commerce market was valued at \$750 billion in 2016, making it the largest market in the world and worth more than the US and UK combined. With 650 million internet users – more than any other country in the world – it is also the fastest growing online shopping market. Between 2010 and 2015, e-commerce exploded in China at an unprecedented rate in conjunction with a growth in disposable income and consumption across the country (Shanthi. & Kanniah, 2015). Having now surpassed every other major market in the world, China's e-commerce trajectory can provide us with insights into what the evolution of e-commerce will look like elsewhere: explosive, widespread, and constantly changing. China currently has two major e-commerce markets, which can be categorized in line with the Government's development ranking system. Tier 1 cities - representing the nation's most developed areas - are at the cutting edge of online and mobile commerce, while Tier 2 cities are increasingly spending across mobile, WeChat, and Alibaba commerce.

Alibaba Group is committed to 'making it easy to do business anywhere' and to empowering global SMEs and consumers. By providing new business infrastructures for the Internet era – from e-commerce platforms, inclusive finance and smart logistics to big data, cloud computing and cross-border trade services – the Group is helping SMEs to better 'source globally, sell globally' and to seek ever more innovative development (Diao, 2015).

A study by Zhou, et al. (2011) examined factors that increased and decreased online Chinese consumers' purchasing. They discovered that perceived positive service quality has a significant influence on consumers' increase of online purchasing while perceived poor website quality resulted in a decrease of online purchasing. Zhou et al. (2011) suggest that e-retailers should be mindful that different strategies must be pursued if the desired effect is to increase online shopping or reduce online shopping defectors. According to Richards and Shen (2006) different shopping channels such as Internet shopping, brick-and mortar shopping, catalog shopping and TV shopping provide consumers different avenues to their purchased objects. After an exploratory study on the factors influencing Chinese consumers' Internet adoption as a medium for shopping.

According to Jiguang's report at the end of November 2018, the total number of online shoppers using Chinese e-commerce apps installed on their mobile devices grew from 207 million to 783 million within just one year.

The penetration of e-commerce in China has reached 71.1% of the total Chinese population. With the population of China reaching over 1.4 billion this means there are over a billion people on China's shopping apps. In terms of spending, e-marketer estimates that spending on China's shopping apps reached USD 1.53 trillion in near future. With China shopping apps experiencing such tremendous growth, competition is becoming more and fiercer. New players are forced to fight for even a sliver of market share but nonetheless, there has been a steady stream of new entrants to the market causing constant shifts in the China e-commerce landscape (Gehrt, Onzo, Fujita, & Rajan 2007).

China, today is characterized by consumer's mobile using behavior, vibrant social e-commerce adoption and a ubiquitous digital payments infrastructure. In addition, the market is fiercely competitive and the most innovative survive in the dynamic retail environment. Many retailers and brand started to embrace the growth of digital by experimenting with online. As with many trends in China, Alibaba is also at the forefront of omni-channel innovation with their new retail model. Alibaba wants to attract more retailers to a new model that blurs the traditional lines between offline and online. This new model uses integrated data and logistics to enable retailers to sell more goods. T-mall allows consumers to claim benefits whenever they shop and enable brands capture end to end consumer data. Alibaba perceives the offline and online retail worlds converging. Customers can make purchases straight from the store as well as they can use the mobile app and do the Alipay payment in order to enjoy deliveries of fresh food within two hours if they live 5 km radius at their door step.

Materials and methods

This research used the mix methodology to collect the data with quantitative and qualitative aspects. The primary data were collected with questionnaire and the structured interviews. The questionnaire was filled by 75 foreign students who stayed during the COVID-19 period in China. Interviews were conducted with 8 foreign students who stayed in the Communication University of China, Beijing to collect more depth of the data. Data were collected with two weeks of period and the questionnaire was made with Chinese mini program app. The online interviews were conducted via WeChat, a social networking site.

The raw data gathered through questionnaire were analyzed with using SPSS. Descriptive analysis and regression analysis were conducted to analyze the data gathered through questionnaire. The interviews conducted with a semi-structured question also supported to find more information.

The collected data with the questionnaire is presented as below. The descriptive analyses were conducted to analyze the demographic factors. The present education status of the participants is indicated as below.

Figure 1: (Education)

The result of the data analysis indicated that of the total 75 students from whom data was collected, 48% of students were pursuing Bachelor's degree, 33.3% were pursuing Master's degree and 17.3% were pursuing Doctoral Degree (PhD) in China. The majority of the sample is Bachelor degree holders in the study.

The Demographic factor Gender indicated the below results

Figure 2: (Gender)

The above figure indicates the 45.3% female participation and 53.3% male participation in this study. This also indicated that majority of the participants are male.

The below mentioned that the majority of the foreign students used the online shopping apps during the COVID-19 period for do their daily life shopping.

Figure 2; (Using online shopping apps)

The above figure mentioned that the 22.6% didn't used the online applications to do shopping and 77% used the online applications to do their shopping which can be mentioned as the majority.

The regression analysis was conducted to identify the factors which influenced the foreign students to use the online shopping apps during the COVID-19 period in China.

Model	Coefficients ^a				
	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	2.482	0.649		3.827	0.000
Trustworthiness	0.742	0.187	0.491	3.970	0.000
Efficiency	0.525	0.127	0.477	4.132	0.000
User Friendly	0.822	0.140	0.674	5.887	0.000
Cost effective	0.194	0.126	0.139	1.549	0.126

a. Dependent Variable: Online Shopping

Table 1: Regression Analysis

The above-mentioned table explains that the Trustworthiness, Efficiency, User friendliness to use the onlineshopping apps during the COVID-19 have the positive significance. This gives interesting finding that cost effectiveness has negative significance towards using the online shopping app during the COVID-19 period in China.

According to the regression analysis it shows that trustworthiness has a significant impact towards the online shopping of foreign students during the COVID-19 period in China. It can be more clarified, coefficient beta (b) = .491, t = 3.970 and the p value 0.000 (p =0.000). The p value is smaller than 0.05 means the trustworthiness has a significant impact towards online shopping. Therefore, every one unit additional in factor trustworthiness is expecting the online shopping will lead to increase by 0.491 units.

Secondly, regression analysis shows that efficiency has a significant impact towards the online shopping of foreign students during the COVID-19 period in China. It can be more clarified, coefficient beta (b) = .477, t = 4.132 and the p value 0.000 (p =0.000). The p value is smaller than 0.05 means the efficiency has a significant impact towards online shopping. Therefore, every one unit additional in factor efficiency is expecting the online shopping will lead to increase by 0.477 units.

Thirdly, regression analysis shows that user friendliness has a significant impact towards the online shopping of foreign students during the COVID-19 period in China. It can be more clarified, coefficient beta (b) = 674, t = 5.887 and the p value 0.000 (p =0.000). The p value is smaller than 0.05 means the efficiency has a significant impact towards online shopping. Therefore, every one unit additional in factor efficiency is expecting the online shopping will lead to increase by 0.674 units.

Finally, regression analysis shows that cost effectiveness has a negative impact towards the online shopping of foreign students during the COVID-19 period in China. It shows as p value 0. 126 (p=0.126). The p value

is higher than 0.05 means the cost effectiveness has a negative impact towards the online shopping.

During recent years China developed their future with the online shopping and it became viral among Chinese and foreigners who resides in China. In daily life most of the apparel, shoes, jewelries, kitchen equipment's, beddings, and toiletries among others used to be purchase through online in China. During the COVID-19 period when the most of the provinces in China went for the lock down the trend of online shopping increased. Foreign students staying at the university were not allowed to go out in a bid to prevent them from the rapid spread of the virus. This forced many students who have not used the online shopping apps to use it. Not only has that, those who used to order apparels and other stuffed online started ordering even groceries (meat, vegetables, rice fruits spices etc. and food online as they cannot move out.

The analysis of the interview answers showed that the perception of the foreign students about the online shopping during the COVID-19 in China is highly positive. Majority of the students said that they used to buy the all essentials with online shopping apps during confinement period in China. According to the interview results it has high efficiency of receiving groceries and goods. Most of the grocery items used to deliver to door step within an hour. As per the majority's view point the online shopping apps has high trustworthiness as the products they received were good and the food items, meat and vegetables were fresh. The majority of the interviewees also mentioned that it is very easy to use as it has an option to chat with the seller, easy to select and easy to purchase with the digital money. The results of the interviews indicated that the cost effectiveness is not really good in online shopping as the offline shopping is cheaper than the online. This factor gave the negative feedback of using the online shopping apps during the COVID-19 period. China has been using the digital money from many years ago since the Chinese social media introduced the feature of digital wallet.

According to the interview results, majority is satisfied with the online shopping during the COVID-19. They indicated high efficiency in terms of trustworthiness and user friendliness. Majority interviewees are highly satisfied with using the online shopping apps during the COVID-19 period. According to the results they were satisfied with the quality of the product and the quick service even during the pandemic. During the pandemic online shopping became a solution for buying all the necessary items and foreign students in China had no problems getting whatever they needed.

As per the majority, they used Tmall online shopping app and pinduoduo apps to purchase most of the vegetables and the daily needed food items. They also mentioned that the mei ri you xian, meituan, ele me (you are hungry), multipoint, and duo dian apps were also used to purchase the daily needed food and grocery items. The Tmall and the pinduoduo gave high efficiency of delivering the quality goods at the door step. Taobao and JD.com was used highly to purchase the rest of the needed things. As per the interview results all apps has high user friendliness which they gave good service during the pandemic.

There are few challenges identified in this research using the online shopping, that most of the online shopping apps are in the Chinese language and it is difficult to search more facilities which app offers due to the language barrier. It is also difficult to contact the seller when the texts are delivered in English and all the

sellers used to communicate in Chinese. All the interviewees mentioned that the language was the major barrier for online shopping. They also mentioned that though the food items were of good quality and were fresh, in some cases other items like clothes, shoes and bags need to meet the quality expectation as seen in the picture. This is the other problem faced by the foreigners in China mainly because they cannot read and understand the description of product mentioned in the app. However, in terms of overall satisfaction, majority of the foreigners who did online shopping during COVID-19 expressed that they are highly satisfied with the service even during the pandemic.

This research tested 6 hypotheses of which 5 hypotheses are positive and 1 hypothesis resulted negative. The below table indicated the results as below.

Hypothesis	Conclusion
H1: Foreign students have positive perception towards online shopping during the COVID-19 period in China	Supported
H2: Foreign Students have positive satisfaction towards online shopping during the COVID-19 period in China	Supported
H3: Trust worthy to use the online shopping apps has a positive significant	Supported
H4: Efficient in delivery to use the online shopping apps has a positive significant	Supported
H5: User friendliness to use the online shopping apps has a positive significant	Supported
H6: Cost effectiveness to use the online shopping apps has a positive significant	Unsupported

Table 2: Tested Hypothesis

Conclusion

The data analysis conducted to identify the perception of foreign students about online shopping during COVID- 19 in China showed that they had positive perception towards online shopping and were highly satisfied. Three factors indicated as positive significant factors for online shopping such as trustworthiness, efficiency and user friendliness. Cost effectiveness gave negative results of online shopping during the pandemic time in China.

This research has indicated few of the challenges such as language barrier and the quality concerns (in some cases) while buying items other than food products. This research also indicated online shopping apps used to

purchase daily items during the pandemic while the students were confined in the universities in China such as mainly Tmall, puoduo puoduo, meituan, Taobao and JD.com among others.

This research has few limitations which can be addressed by the future researchers. The sample size can be identified as one of the research limitations. For this study only 4 factors were taken into consideration which can be added in the further study. In addition to this, the study has been conducted only among foreign students in China and the further study can be carried out among Chinese students. Similarly, the interviews were carried out only among the students of Communication University of China. For the future study, research among the students of different university can bring out different perspectives.

The author suggests the online shopping app to add language options mainly English language in their system so that it becomes user friendly for foreigners. The retailers should be advised to deliver the quality goods and suggested not to compromise on quality of the products being delivered. The online shopping apps usage in China for day to day items will definitely be more developed in near future in China and the interface will be made more users friendly. The findings indicate that more the users friendly the apps are made, there is high chances the foreigners will completely start relying on online apps for shopping all the necessary items including daily essentials like groceries and ready-made food items.

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